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EXPERIMENTAL MODEL OF PSYCHOGENIC STRESS AND SELF-REGULATORY BEHAVIOR

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Abstract: Changes of compensatory mechanisms of the white laboratory rats at different stages of psychogenic stress were studied. For modeling of the psychogenic stress, the modified model of active avoidance response was used. It was established that at different stages of stress development (I, II and III), in the conditions of different complexity experiment, the fear and anxiety responses dominate in the rats. In addition, the behavior showed by them is of self-regulatory compensatory nature, it is of regular character and show up in certain proportion between the behavior acts. The described behavior is interpreted as revealing of the biologically positive stress playing adaptive role, improves, strengthens resistivity to stress stimulus and ensures homeostasis of psychics.

Keywords: psychogenic stress, emotion, behavior, adaptation, rats.

Introduction: on the basis of clinical and experimental data the conception of the higher nervous activity pathologies, and the psychogenic stress among them. Many researchers are interested in the stress issues and they are still of great significance. In many cases the term ‘stress’ is widely used to designate biologically adverse, dangerous, undesirable condition, certainly requiring treatment, while the most important function of the stress is to protect the organism from the action of extremely powerful stimulus. Attention should be paid to involvement of the mechanisms causing improvement of the organism resistance to the stress factors endangering health.

Research goal and objectives: in formation of psychogenic stress, particular attention should be paid to studying of the behavior and emotional characteristics contributing to the organism adaptation to more severe environmental conditions. In the experimental studies of the animals there was developed model of psychogenic stress allowing identification and recording of the behavior and emotional characteristics at different levels (stages) of stress development. Goal of our research included identification of the behavioral components of the brain self-regulatory action, clarification of the regularities of behavioral acts revealing in the conditions of psychogenic stress caused by unfavorable combination of the “information triad” at different stages.

Materials and methods: we have studied the changes of behavioral and emotional characteristics at different stages of psychogenic stress development applying the following method:

1. For the purpose of assessment of the emotional condition of animals we applied the “open field” (0) and “pro-conflict” (10) test methods.

2. For modeling of the psychogenic test, we have applied the modified model of active avoidance response (4). The mentioned model allows modeling of long-lasting psychogenic stress

in animals, against the background of which assessment of different behavior characteristics in the animals is possible.

Experimental studies were conducted on 60 males of white laboratory rats of 180-200 g weight, divided into two groups”

In the group I the experiments were conducting applying the modified model of active avoidance response, the experiment commenced with:

- Development and strengthening of the active avoidance response to the first conditional signal (metronome – 2 Hz).
- Development and strengthening of the active avoidance response to two conditional signals (metronome – 2 Hz, tone – 500 Hz).
- “Unification of two active avoidance responses for 14 days, their simultaneous testing in random order (Gellerman stochastic program) (8)

In the animals of group II (intact rats) we have studied the behavioral and emotional characteristics by means of the “open field” and “pro-conflict” tests.

Experimental cage for the modified model of active avoidance response consists of three sections of equal size (20x20x35 cm) divided by the barriers of 10 cm height. On the right and left side walls of the cage there are attached the sources of sound signals (metronome – 2 Hz and tone – 500 Hz). The floor and barriers of all three sections of the “stress-box” were electrified (40 V AC), allowing painful electric stimulation of the rat paws.

Stage I of stressing – for the purpose of elaboration and strengthening of active avoidance response to the first conditional signal (metronome – 2 Hz) we placed the animal into the central (starting) section of the cage for 60 seconds and further turned on the conditional signal (metronome – 2 Hz), with the isolated action time of 5 seconds, for this time the rat had to move to the side signaled right section (the left section was closed by the barrier). If the animal failed to perform the mentioned action, after expiry of the isolated action of the audio signal time (5 sec), it’s paws were stimulated by electricity. For 10 seconds after moving to the side section the rat had to return to the starting section, otherwise, it received the electric stimulation again. Active avoidance response was regarded as elaborated, when the number of proper responses to metronome for sequence of five experimental days achieved 80% criterion. After this we commenced elaboration and strengthening of active avoidance response to the second conditional signal (tone – 500 Hz).

Stage II of stressing – after elaboration and strengthening of the active avoidance response to the first conditional stressor (metronome – 2 Hz) we commenced elaboration and strengthening of active avoidance response to the second conditional signal (tone – 500 Hz). The animal was again placed into the central section of “stress box”. This time it had to perform active avoidance response to the second conditional signal (tone - 500 Hz), i.e. in the period of isolated action of the audio signal for 5 seconds the rat had to move to the left section of the “stress box” and for 10 seconds it had to return to the starting section. In the event of active avoidance response of the mentioned type the rat was punished and received painful electric pulse, persisting until the animal performs active self-protecting response. In elaboration of the active avoidance response to both, the tone and metronome, the conditional signal was given to the animal only when it was in the starting section. Each round included 20 tests with one-minute intervals between the signals.

Stage III of stressing – after elaboration and strengthening of two active avoidance responses separately, we commenced testing of active avoidance response to the tone and metronome within single test. We again placed the animal in the central section of the “stress box”. This time,

the barriers were removed from the experimental cage and the rat was free to move to both, right and left sections of the cage. At this stage of the experiment the rat had to perform the following actions: at a time of metronome signal the animal had to move to the right section of the “stress box” and return to the initial point within 10 seconds; and in response to the tone – to the left section and return within 10 seconds.

In the event of incorrect response to the conditional signals, the animal’s paws received painful electric pulse. Alteration of the conditional signals (metronome, tone) was provided according to Gellerman stochastic program (8), i.e. using the signals randomly, with equal probabilities (50/50). Each following conditional signal, with one-minute intervals, was given to the animal only when it was in the central section.

At all three stages of the experiment we have recorded the following data: percentage of the correct responses to the signal, duration of vertical and horizontal standing and grooming, number of the movements between signals, raising of head and fecal boluses.

Results and discussion: analysis of the behavior showed by the animals in the different stress situations, showed that in the conditions of experiments of different complexities the rats’ behavior does not change qualitatively, only changes of proportion between the behavioral acts take place. In particular, to achieve the criterion of elaboration and strengthening of active avoidance response to the first stimulus (metronome – 2 Hz) the animal required 120-160 impacts (6-8 days) (Fig. 1).

Figure1. Dynamics of active avoidance response elaboration in the experimental rats.

In the unfamiliar environment for the rat, with unusual stressor, the animal faced the self-defense problem; it had to avoid painful impact of electricity. This was associated with decision-making, growth of emotional strain and this reflects on the behavior characteristics: duration of vertical standing (4.7 ± 2.3) and movements between the signals (3.4 ± 1.2) was much higher than “grooming” (0.6 ± 0.5) and horizontal standing (2.6 ± 1.1) duration characteristics and number of head raising (22.2 ± 7.8) was higher than number of fecal boluses (5.6 ± 1.7) (Table 1).

Table 1. Statistical evaluation of the behavioral characteristics in the period of active avoidance response elaboration-strengthening and simultaneous testing of two active avoidance responses within single experiment in the test rats.

Behavior forms	Stage I(1)	Stage II (2)	Stage III (3)		

	Avg	SD	Avg	SD	Avg	SD	P 1-2	P 2-3
Vertical standing	4.7	2.3	1.9	0.8	4	0.9	0.009	0.0001
Horizontal standing	2.6	1.1	3.9	0.7	0.3	0.2	0.009	0.02
Raising of the head	22.2	7.8	25.3	6.2	13.6	4	0.04	0.05
Fecal boluses	5.6	1.7	2.7	0.5	5.2	1.1	0.001	0.0001
Inter-signal moves	3.4	1.2	1.7	0.5	3.8	1.4	0.009	0.003
Grooming	0.6	0.5	2.1	1.1	0.1	0.1	0.005	0.02

At the following stage of experiment – with the second audio stressor (tone – 500 Hz) we checked firmness of the active avoidance response elaborated for 3-4 days (60-80 impacts) (Fig. 1) In such situation the rats showed automated adequate self-defense behavior, as they became the animals adapted to the experimental environment. It is known that such situation is characterized with less emotional strain (due to reduction of painful stimulation), demonstrated by change of proportions between the behavioral acts: in particular, compared with the first step, durations of “grooming” ($2.1 \pm 1.1 = 0.005$) and horizontal standing ($3.9 \pm 0.7 = 0.009$) has reliably increased while rates of vertical standings ($1.9 \pm 0.8 = 0.009$), inter-signal movements ($1.7 \pm 0.5 = 0.009$) and fecal boluses ($2.7 \pm 0.5 = 0.001$) decreased (Table 1). Numerous experimental studies show that such responses reflect the animal’s emotional conditions, Vertical standing expresses the rat’s strong emotional strain, “grooming” takes place in the medium severity conflict situations and it is not demonstrated at a time of emotional strain. Such behavior showed by the animals – in the conditions of the different complexity experiments, solving of the challenge, serves to discharge of emotional strain and is regarded as self-regulating behavior (4, 5). In 14-day testing of two active avoidance responses simultaneously the percentage of correct responses did not exceed 30-45% (Fig. 1) and this was maintained for 14 days. At this stage of experiment, formation of active avoidance response did not take place, as the brain operates in the conditions of unfavorable combination of the “information triad” factors. In particular, for long time the rats were in the conditions of high motivation, with deficiency of time and pragmatic information and for them, this was a challenge and strong stress factor on higher nervous function (4). Thus, in 14-day testing of two active avoidance responses simultaneously the rats were in chronic psychogenic stress conditions. Comparing with the period of firm self-defense responses, at this stage of testing, duration of vertical standing ($4 \pm 0.9 = 0.0001$), rates of inter-signal movements ($3.8 \pm 1.4 = 0.003$) and fecal boluses ($5.2 \pm 1.1 = 0.001$) have reliably increased (Table 1). And such behavior is expression of self-regulatory behavior that is not associated with the conditional signal. As for “grooming”, horizontal standing and number of raisings of head – their rates are much lower, compared with the similar rates of automatized self-defense responses.

According to the literature, general system of brain neuron regulation ensures organism adaptation in the stress situation and it is one of significant components of central regulating mechanism of the organism resistance (6). The mentioned mechanism can be considered as self-regulatory mechanism oriented towards improvement of the organism resistance, in response to the adverse impact (1). It has certain structural-functional organization revealed in a form of specific psychosomatic responses (3, 5).

Behavior showed by the animals at all three stages of psychogenic stress development can be interpreted as biologically positive stress demonstration and reflects self-regulatory action of the brain. Strengthening of the brain self-regulatory action should commence at the stage before disease, where these mechanisms become involved and are prominent. Their targeted strengthening can play decisive role in improvement of the organism resistance to stress factors (2).

We have studied the emotional condition of animals at different stages of psychogenic stress development, before and after stressing, by open field and pro-conflict tests. Compared with the intact rats, elaboration of the self-defense responses – after strengthening, in the open field tests, there was indicated the trend of reduction of investigative activity and latent period of movement activity ($=0.001$) and grooming duration ($=0.003$) increased (Table 2).

Table 2. Statistical evaluation of behavior characteristics at different stages of psychogenic stress development in the experimental rats in open field test.

Behavior forms	Intact (1)		Stage I (2)		Stage II (3)		Stage III (4)		P 1-2	P 2-3	P 3-4
	Ave.	SD	Ave.	SD	Ave.	SD	Ave.	SD			
Moving to the center	1	1	2	0.5	2.8	0.7	3.5	1.1	0.008	0.05	0.08
Crossed squares	37.5	15.6	27.8	19.7	15.5	8.9	5.7	3.6	0.1	0.05	0.003
Vertical standing	17.2	4.9	10.5	4.8	8.7	5.5	3.4	1.9	0.003	0.2	0.007
Hole reflex	4.4	1.7	2.5	0.7	1.4	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.004	0.002	0.02
Head raising	20.6	9.7	15.5	2.6	12.1	4.6	6.3	2	0.07	0.03	0.001
Fecal boluses	2	2	0.7	1.2	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.7	0.06	0.3	0.2
Latent period	0.8	0.3	3	1.2	5	0.5	6.7	1.3	0.05	0.0001	0.001
Grooming	16.3	5.4	28.3	8.9	43.5	15.1	88.3	28.7	0.001	0.009	0.0003

Reduction of search activity in open field points to strengthening of emotional strain (9). Reasonability of this view is supported by the results of testing in pro-conflict situation. Compared with the intact rats, in the experimental rats, after elaboration of active avoidance response ($=0.001$) and simultaneous 14-day testing ($=0.002$), number of punished acts of water drinking have reduced reliably (Table 3). According to this test, small number of the drinking acts punished with electricity is indicator of strengthening of anxiety response (7).

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Table 3. Statistical evaluation of behavioral characteristics at different stages of psychogenic stress development by pro-conflict test in experimental rats.

Number of drinking acts punished with electricity	Intact (1)		Stage I (2)		Stage II (3)		Stage III (4)		P 1-2	P 2-3	P 3-4
	Avg.	SD	Avg.	SD	Avg.	SD	Avg.	SD			

Experimental rats	8.4	4.5	3	0.7	1.5	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.001	0.002	0.004
Intact rats	4.7	3.3	2.7	0.5	1.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.09	0.002	0.008

Conclusion: thus, based on the behavioral and emotional characteristics obtained in our experiments on stressed rats and data from medical literature, we can conclude the following: in testing self-defense responses of different complexity at different stages of psychogenic stress development, the fear and anxiety responses dominate in the animals. Behavior showed by the rats ensures organism adaptation in stress situation, as well as demonstration of self-regulatory action of the brain, as reflected in certain proportions between the behavioral acts. The described behavior can be interpreted as demonstration of biologically positive stress playing adaptive role, improving, strengthening resistance to stressors and ensuring homeostasis of psychics.

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